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Confwatcher: a tool for economists to make the search for conferences and special issues more efficient and transparent

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Abstract: Hundreds of conferences, seminars and workshops in economics are organized worldwide every year. Being able to get a full information on their content and dates, in a more efficient and transparent way, is key for economists as it should enable them to submit their papers in the right places, and then publish them in better conditions, especially when the event is linked to a special issue. Conversely, for organizers, making sure that most publicity is made and that economists who have written interesting papers in the scope of the event have the information and may then envisage to submit their articles is important to match the expected standard of the event. Using datascience technics (web-scraping and text analysis), Confwatcher is a tool that proposes a simple interface to identify conferences with call for papers (and possibly special issues) among institutions (central banks, international organizations, research centers, journals, economists' associations...) that propose most high-quality events.

JEL Codes: A1

Keywords: Conferences, workshops, seminars, publications, call for paper, special issue, presentation, submission.

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The market for conferences in economics is large, but with partial information

The market for conferences has a limited number of suppliers on the one hand, and many economists on the other hand have the potential to submit one or several papers. Conference can be with general or more specialized topics, and it is quite common to have several organizers, whether institutions like central banks, international organizations, research agencies, ministries (usually Treasuries or assimilated), think tanks, or universities/schools and journals.

Conferences may also propose some special issues, in order to publish in a journal associated to the event. These special issues are of particular interest as they usually propose to publish in a field that is well defined in advance, which increases the likelihood for an economist of matching between the theme of his/her article and the (special) issue of the Journal, and with shorter time constraints.

Beyond special issues, presenting a paper in a high-quality conference has some implications for future outcomes for publication. Indeed, as shown by Gorodnichenko et al. (2021) who examine the contribution of conference presentation to publishing outlook, conference presentations are positively related to the likelihood of publishing in high-quality journals. Evidence for the effectiveness of conferences in promoting academic impact is confirmed by Leite Lopez de Leon & McQuillin (2020), who exploit the cancellation-due to Hurricane Isaac- of the 2012 American Political Science Association Annual Meeting.

Every year, hundreds of high-quality events are organized in economics. The quality of an event, whether it is called a conference, a workshop or a seminar can be assessed through the ranking of the institution (for example in the RePEc classification: [Economic Institution Rankings | IDEAS/RePEc](#)) and/or of the participants, whether keynote speakers, discussants, or economists who present the papers (see the ranking of economists: [Economist Rankings | IDEAS/RePEc](#)).

The location of the conference also plays a key role, as underlined by Günther et al. (2017), who find that “the location of the presentation is at least as important for the number of academics attending a talk as the combined effect of the person presenting and the paper presented”.

Location is also identified as a key element for the choice of a conference, in the specific field of labour economics, coming second after the keynote speakers, as found by Borghans et al. (2010). The aim of this paper is to identify the preferences of participants with respect to conference characteristics. Based on a sample of European labour economists, preferences are measured asking to participants to choose between hypothetical European Association of Labour Economists (EALE) conferences.

In spite of existing websites (for example <https://www.econbiz.de/Events/Results> or [INOMICS | The Site for Economists](#)) that propose lists of conferences, these remain limited because in most cases, the organizers of the event need to register it on corresponding websites, which is not systematically done since it is costly for organizers. Besides, there is not a single website with a leading position that would centralize all the information. Hence, economists who search for a conference in their domain need to pay some variable costs to get the information in real time. This represents, in aggregate terms, important losses either because of the investment in time to get the accurate information or due to lost opportunities when a missed conference

happened to have high potential for an economist in terms of visibility or publication opportunities (either because the conference was associated to a special issue, or because a potential future referee was present).

The use of datascience techniques enables to construct a centralized and updated tool

Keeping in mind abovementioned shortcomings when conference organizers are required to post their events on a given platform, which will not concentrate a sizeable enough fraction of key events anyway, another solution may be envisaged, based on web-scraping and text analysis.

The use of web-scraping enables indeed to identify and include events without requiring any intervention from the organizers, which guarantees that there are no or as little as possible information missed.

In complement of web-scraping that scrutinizes potentially interesting conferences, text analysis is used to check the occurrence of one or several keywords in the title or the description of the event.

An initial set of websites to be covered has been chosen (see Annex 1) and the list can be completed by users by suggesting to add other websites (see the icon “Ask for a new item” on the page listing institutions of ConfWatcher: [“ConfWatcher \(conferences.eu.pythonanywhere.com\)”](http://conferences.eu.pythonanywhere.com)), with a limited marginal cost (in average, it represents around two hours to add a website).

In the whole, many variable costs are saved, on the side of both the organizers and the economists searching to submit their papers. On the side of ConfWatcher, the costs are limited and centralized: there is a fixed cost to set the initial list of websites and a variable cost to update them.

Shortcomings and tips to optimize the use of ConfWatcher

Still, the use of web-scraping and text analysis may have a few shortcomings. Since a given event may be organized and present on the website of several institutions, there may be some duplicates. Besides, a search by keyword may lead to have too many results (which advocates to use several keywords / combination of keywords using the “AND” option to refine the search) but in both cases, there should be as little missed event as possible (even if ConfWatcher cannot guarantee total exhaustiveness).

To have a more practical view to use ConfWatcher, see Annex 2.

References

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Günther I., Grosse M. & Klasen S. (2017), How to Attract an Audience at a Conference: Paper, Person or Place? *German Economic Review*, Vol. 18, Issue 4, pp. 468-491.

Leite Lopez de Leon F. & McQuillin B. (2020), The Role of Conferences on the Pathway to Academic Impact Evidence from a Natural Experiment, *Journal of Human Resources*, Vol. 55, Issue 1, pp. 164-193.

Annex 1: Choice and list (by alphabetical order)⁵ of the institutions covered by ConfWatcher

In order to have as full a coverage as possible, the choice of the institutions to be covered is key. To have a coverage as complete as possible, institutions have been envisaged in the most systematic way:

- Central banks: most important central banks in the world have been covered, including regional Feds that propose a significant enough number of events, the BIS (Bank for International Settlements) and the ECB/most important members of the Eurosystem.
- International organizations such as World Bank or IMF have been included.
- Think tanks: to capture as much as possible the most influential think tanks in economics, the list from RePEc available on the following link: [Economics rankings: Think Tanks | IDEAS/RePEc](#) (top 25% think tanks) has been used. It appears that most of them do not issue conferences with call for papers or, if they do so, they usually organize them jointly with other institutions that are captured. NBER, IZA, CPER, Ifo, Bruegel and CEPII have been included.
- Academic Journals/ Universities: rankings available in REPEC ([Economic Institution Rankings | IDEAS/RePEc](#), top 10% Economic Institutions) and in the French CNRS (Categorization of Journals in Economics and Management), which stopped in 2020 (<https://docs.google.com/viewer?a=v&pid=sites&srcid=ZGVmYXVsdGRvbWFpbnczZWNOaW9uMzdjbnJzfGd4OjE3YjAxMzNlZTYyNjU2MGM>), but this ranking still contains most important journals, since journals created in the meantime are not likely to have enough weight.

⁵ The list will expand over time, depending partly on proposals of adding by users.

The initial list of Institutions covered by ConfWatcher is as follows:

- Academy of Management
- American Economic Association (AEA)
- Asian Development Bank
- Association Française de Science Economique (AFSE)
- Banca d'Italia (Central Bank)
- Banco de Espana (Central Bank)
- Bank for International Settlements
- Bank of Canada (Central Bank)
- Bank of England (Central Bank)
- Bank of Japan (Central Bank)
- Banque de France (Central Bank)
- Bruegel
- Bundesbank (Central Bank)
- Center for Economic Studies (CESifo)
- Centre d'etudes prospectives et d'informations internationales (CEPII)
- Centre for Economic Policy Research (CEPR)
- De Nederlandsche Bank (Central Bank)
- Direction générale du Trésor
- Emerald Publishing Journal
- European (Central Bank) (Central Bank)
- European Economic Association (EEA)
- Federal Reserve Bank of Cleveland (Central Bank)
- Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis (Central Bank)
- Federal Reserve Bank of New York (Central Bank)
- Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco (Central Bank)
- Institute of Labor Economics (IZA)
- International Monetary Fund (IMF)
- Journal of International Economics (Journal)
- Leibniz Institute for Economic Research (IFO)
- National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER)
- Norges Bank (Central Bank)
- Royal Economic Society (RES)
- Sveriges Riksbank (Central Bank)
- Swiss National Bank (Central Bank)
- The Econometric Society
- The Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences
- World Bank

Annex 2: how to use Confwatcher in practice

ConfWatcher allows to find future conferences economists can attend, and journals they can submit to.

All these events are from the institutions' websites. There may be missing information or errors. However, the tool allows to have an overview of all the events, organized by the world's major [economic and financial institutions](#), that may be of interest to economists.

Searches can be performed on the following link [here](#). Users are invited to fill in the fields, keeping in mind that they are optional, so that all the events can be seen.

Besides economists, people in charge to organize a conference in economics, whether economists or administrative staff may also find it useful to have a quite encompassing picture of future events, to find periods with fewer events to avoid overlaps.

Use of the search bar

Use the search bar to find the topics that interest you.

Write down the keywords you want to appear in the event content. With each new word you add, you increase the number of results. If you prefer to reduce the number of possibilities, use the AND operator between the keywords.

If you want to search for groups of words or bits of sentences with words in a given order, the user should type all the words in the right order using "...", for example:

✓ “monetary policy” AND inflation

✓ dwelling AND "web scraping" AND prices europe

✗ bankANDinflation is wrong as there should be some space before and after « AND ». The right thing to write is rather : bank AND inflation

✗ Banque de France AND inflation is also wrong. The right search is rather: "Banque de France" AND inflation

✗ europe and rate is also wrong since « AND » should be written with capital letters : europe AND rate

Add a time range

Enter start and end dates to view only the events during the period of your choice.

By selecting dates for the event, you will only see the corresponding events and the events whose date is unknown by our service, but for which you will be able to consult the official conference page.

✓ When dates are available:

Call for paper - Submission deadline : June 30, 2022

6^{ème} Atelier du groupe de recherche du SEBC sur l'économie monétaire

Paris - Oct. 11, 2022

— From *Banque de France*

[View details](#)

✘ When the dates are not available, to avoid the risk of missing an event, this remains displayed by default:

Conference

Annual Research Conference of the Dutch Central Bank -- Inflation Strikes Back: Drivers and Policy

Amsterdam, Netherlands

— From *De Nederlandsche Bank*

[View details](#)

How to find special issues

Check the 'Special Issue' option if this is a requirement for you.

By checking this box, you will only see events with a 'Special Issue'.

But if you don't check it, you can always identify 'Special Issue' by looking at the red flag in the top right corner of the event, as shown in the following image:

Call for paper - Submission deadline : June 17, 2022

Call for Papers in Spatial Macroeconomics

— From *American Economic Association*

[View details](#)